

Abaya Design for Women: Cultural Sensitivity Management and Style Stability

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Abstract

This study investigates the clothing requirements and preferences of Pakistani Muslim women, particularly focusing on the design and comfort of abayas. With the emergence of modest fashion as a global trend, there has been a growing interest in catering to the specific needs of Muslim women, including those in Pakistan. Qualitative data collection methods were employed to gather insights into the challenges faced by Pakistani Muslim women in traditional abayas, such as discomfort during activities like bike rides and issues with sizing and esclaptor trap. The findings underscore the demand for contemporary and comfortable abaya designs in Pakistan, advocating for improved representation and inclusivity in fashion. The study highlights the desire of Pakistani women to wear stylish gowns while adhering to modest fashion principles. Based on these insights, a new line of abayas has been developed, emphasizing simplicity and versatility to address the diverse needs of Pakistani Muslim women effectively. This research contributes to the ongoing discourse on modest fashion and highlights the importance of inclusive design practices in the fashion industry.

Keywords: *Modest fashion, Pakistani women, Hijab, Abaya, clothing needs, Stability, Management.*

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Introduction

Despite the existing misconception of modest fashion in the West, the fashion industry has accepted the emergence of Muslim fashion icons and lured non-Muslim fashion designers to become involved in modest fashion designs. The combination of religious faith and fashion trends has resulted in the popularity of modest fashion among young women. Followers of modest fashion can be dressed in hijabs and burqas, together with tops, trousers, jackets, or dresses featuring a modest style (Aris, Ibrahim, & Ahmad, 2018). Pakistan is the second largest Muslim country in terms of population (after Indonesia) (Choi, & Kim, 2019). The Shalwar kameez, cAchkan, Sherwani, and Kurta Shalwar are the national dresses of Pakistan (Zabeen, Shams, & Sultana, 2017) Punjabi women wear the straight-cut Punjabi shalwar

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kameez which is most frequently worn (Akou, 2007). In Pakistan, upper and middle-class women in towns wear burqas over their normal clothes in public. In rural areas only elite women wear burqas. The burqa is the most visible dress in Pakistan. It is a garment worn over ordinary clothes and is made of white cotton. Many upper-class women wear a two-piece burqa which is usually black but sometimes navy blue or dark red. It consists of a long cloak and a separate headpiece with a drop-down face veil. Some educated urban women no longer wear the burqa, while some of them wear Hijab as an alternative. The burqa is also not worn by rural peasant women who work in the fields (Laar, et al., 2019). The abaya is a simple, loose over-garment, essentially a robe-like dress, worn by some women in parts of the Muslim world.

The use of the hijab has been on the rise worldwide since the 1970s and is viewed by many Muslims as expressing modesty and faith; it has also been worn for purposes of adornment (Mohamed Nasir, 2022). The Abaya, once a symbol of tradition and modesty, has evolved into a fashionable and versatile garment in Pakistan. Online abaya shopping in Pakistan offers women more convenience, blending tradition and modernity, allowing them to express themselves while upholding cultural values (Sethi, & Shen, 2021). The Abaya teaches Muslim women to concentrate on their inner beauty which, on contrary to outer beauty, increases in years that pass (de Souza, 2024). There are some problems for those women who struggle to wear an abaya for work, university and college students of Pakistan, during travel, and married women for comfort, as:

- Tripping on stairs
- Escalator traps
- Size of Abaya
- Sleeve of Abaya
- Bike Ride
- In the Rainy season

This research aims to explore the modest fashion in the abaya and solve the abaya problems. In Pakistan, women wear modest clothing. They prefer it because it covers the body curve and is comfortable. Modest clothing common in Pakistan is the Abaya or burqa with a Hijab or hijab covering the head and hair. I aim to design an innovative Abaya for Pakistani women fulfilling their needs. They want a trendy and stylish Abaya. Pakistani Abaya designs are mostly the same. Mostly Women buy their Abayas from Saudi Arabia and Dubai. Women like the simplest Abayas that can be worn in university, Events, Formal Wear, Casual Wear, semiformal wear, Celebration, etc. My study purpose is to design simple, reversible, and solve Abaya Problems.

Literature Review

Abaya in Islamic Context

Muslims in Britain and cosmopolitan cities throughout the West are increasingly choosing to express their identity and faith through dress, whether by wearing colorful headscarves, austere black garments, or creative new forms of Islamic fashion. It examines how different ideas of fashion, politics, faith, freedom, beauty, modesty, and cultural diversity are articulated by young British Muslims as they seek out clothes that best express their identities, perspectives, and concerns. It also explores the wider social and political effects of their clothing choices on the development of transnational cultural formations and multicultural urban spaces (Lajevardi, Mårtensson, & Vernby, 2024). The abaya has consequently come to be associated with humility and piety. Women use it to preserve their dignity or guard from unwelcome focus (Ballout, 2024).

Types of Abayas and Use

This long black cloak mentioned before is called an abaya. But there are a lot of variations in abaya styles. Traditional and modern abayas are the two types of abayas used in this study. For this purpose, this article focuses on the modern abaya, though I do describe the traditional one as well. Kelly has a wonderful conversation about the abaya in Kuwait. An abaya from Kuwait is considered to be more traditional. an "ankle-length black robe that covers all but the face, hands, and feet" (Kelly, 2010). It is shapeless, loose-fitting, and cape-like, and is preferred by older women. The contemporary abaya is more form-fitting, usually decorated with embroidery and sequins, and perhaps even Swarovski crystals, and is preferred by younger women. It can have beads and patches of different colored fabric. A young woman from Jordan who now resides in Qatar, Hala Akkawi, stated "The Qataris put the abaya on as it is of the traditions and norms." At present, abayas with plenty of patterns, designs, etc., are trendy. Although black remains the color, others have vibrant designs on the back, sleeves, or inside. A combination of daily clothing worn with abaya loses less body heat compared to daily worn clothing alone, irrespective of abaya designs and fabric types (Tashkandi, Kanesalingam, & Wang, 2014). the Abaya fabrics with different weave structures, fiber composition, and fabric weight have a greater influence on the fabric's thermal comfort performance (Tashkandi, Wang, & Kanesalingam, 2013). Women wear the abaya in mixed company in public, such as shopping malls. Author Le Renard describes the abaya as a garment that is not worn continuously throughout the day but rather as a cover when frequenting mixed-sex spaces (Le Renard, 2008). There are different types of Islamic female clothing Burqa, chador, Shayla, khimar, and Niqab.

Pakistan

Pakistan is the world's fifth most populous country. Pakistan stands at eighth for the export of textile commodities in Asia. Fashion Industry of Pakistan has been growing fast for a decade now (Zeb, Rashid, & Javeed, 2011). Nannini et al. (2020) experienced clothing as conveying identity and emotion, through these design minutiae. Increasing numbers of women are engaging in the development and discussion of modest dressing; a movement matched by a growing media and popular demand for intelligent commentary about the topic. Modest Fashion sets out to meet that need. Young Muslim women use multiple fashion systems to negotiate religion, identity, and ethnicity (Lewis, 2015). In Pakistan, the topic of the hijab is extraordinarily controversial. The veil is constantly a topic of debate and has been for decades now. The Pew Research Center gathered information on several countries, including Pakistan, and came back with results on how people's perceptions of the veil differ across the world. Participants were given pictures of six women wearing different styles of veil along with the question: "What Style of Dress is Appropriate for Women in Public?". The results found that: "In Pakistan, there is an even split (31% vs. 32%) between woman #3 and woman #2, who is wearing a niqab that exposes only her eyes, while nearly a quarter (24%) choose woman #4 (Poushter, 2014). The study indicates a persistent debate among women regarding the most suitable dress, a topic that is expected to persist for years to come. The dress, originally a long black gown with a straight cut to the feet, is a religious veil worn by Muslim women worldwide, serving as formal attire for outings.

Traditionalists argue West's influence is corruption, but the media's diverse range facilitates reflection on traditions, facilitating change and promoting globalized perception (Hassim, 2014). Wilson et al. (2013) studied a variety of subcultures and religious groups that are influenced by the globalization of consumerism and the symbolism of modesty in fashion and argued that current definitions of modesty in media denote two entirely different things, first meaning exposure of the female body and another concerning the diminishing visibility of Muslim women. Pakistan's Muslim majority women wear hijab or burqas, but brands and designers focus on this market. Traditional Pakistani women's clothing includes shalwar, kameez, and dupatta, with embroidery and length varying based on individual taste and country trends. In Pakistan, women cover their heads with dupatta in public, even without a proper hijab or burqa, as it symbolizes respect and religious obligation. Burqa more than representing religious or ethnic identity, is an expressive language for native women to differentiate their personal identity (Mohammadi, & Hazeri, 2021).

The Islamic fashion industry is becoming more diverse and inclusive, and the demand for modest wear is gaining momentum. Muslim-owned brands should adapt to the growing demand for modest, fashionable clothing among the youth, considering the diverse range of Islamic fashion preferences (Hassan, et al., 2018). The abaya has evolved into a fashionable garment, featuring various cuts and designs from top Pakistani designer brands like lamosaik.com. Nowadays, abayas have become more versatile and functional. Keeping in view the demands of modern ladies, abayas have constantly been updated now and then to bring innovation and style to them (Bilal, 2024). This movement became significant during independence and nationalist movements that led to the modern states we know today. Among the types of abayas evaluated, those worn on the head had higher thermal resistance than those worn from the shoulder with tight sleeves. Marginal variations were also observed based on the clothing worn under the abaya (Helmi, Tashkandi, & Wang, 2022). The study of Pakistani women doctors, this research indicates that practicing purdah in the workplace is perceived as doing femininity within the hegemonic masculine workplace culture of Pakistan (Masood, 2019). Surprisingly, Muslims are one of the top consumer groups of luxurious cars, homes, and fashion items despite their ascetical, conservative image. Until now, the entry of foreign companies into the Muslim market has been difficult due to the market's unique qualities; however, the opportunity for preemption in the market is worth attempting (Kim, et al., 2012).

The women inscribe hijab with meanings shaped by their unique cultural standpoints. The hijab functions to define Muslim identity, perform a behavior check, resist sexual objectification, afford more respect, preserve intimate relationships, and provide freedom (Droogsma, 2007). Most of the brands only design traditional clothes. The history of the Hijab portrays that hijab is an ancient custom in Muslims and it has different meanings in different regions, and it varies with time. The hijab is considered a sign of oppression in Western society. Muslim women who wear hijab find it so respectful and according to the hijab is the identity of Muslim women. The hijab is one of the fastest-growing fashion Industries in Middle Eastern countries, but the hijab fashion industry of Pakistan is yet to do wonders. According to Islam, all Muslim women should cover their heads and wear gowns to cover their body curves in public.

The Modest Fashion Market

There has been a surge in the growth of popularity of modest fashion over the past decade among Muslim women regardless of age group because now, dressing styles are viewed as fashion statements rather than religious symbols or obligations (Zabeen, Shams, & Sultana, 2017). Though modest fashion does not relate to any religion of the world, the image is identical with has beneath the way Muslim women don their attires (Menon, Hashim, & Hasim, 2020). Muslim women perceive modest fashion as a fashion trend that is associated with religious symbols and modern trends in mainstream fashion brands, but not forgetting, the marketing strategies of local brands that target the Muslim society. The fact that the demand for modest fashion has extended to Western countries shows that Islamic fashion is no longer dull. Modest fashion also experienced a shift in the fashion landscape, specifically from religious clothing to high-end fashion. Luxury brand names, such as DKNY, Dolce & Gabbana, Max Mara, and Alberta Ferretti are among the brands that understand the significance of the Muslim market trade in modest fashion. The growth in the modest fashion market is expected to reach US\$361 billion by 2023, as Muslims' expenditure on fashion reached US\$270 billion in 2017, according to the State of the Global Islamic Economy Report 2018/19 (Deniz, 2023). There are top abaya brands that is Hafizah Ghazali, Diana Kotb, Lara Ali, Lulu Alhadad, Dina Tokio, Ibtihaj Muhammad, Hana Tajima, Rico Ronaldi, Nurita Harith, Raja Nadia Sabrina, Dian Pelangi, Mohd Hafizi Radzi Woo, Ria Miranda, Vivi Zubedi, Malanie El Turk.

Fashion Conscious

Fashion consciousness is defined as a person's degree of involvement toward fashion as well as styles of attire (Nam, et al., 2007). It also applies to individuals who are highly involved with all goods related to fashion. It is noted that modest fashion brands, marketers as well as retailers need to give attention to fashion consciousness since it plays a significant role in luring Muslim women to purchase fashion attires. Muslim women demonstrate their fashion consciousness by exhibiting individual styles to identify them

personally. The sources of fashion knowledge and fashion uniqueness are the main determinants that merit focus in creating fashion consciousness in modest fashion products. Modest fashion became popular over the past decade among Muslim women of all age groups, who have regarded dressing styles as a fashion statement rather than a religious one (Ara, 2021).

Methodology

The study used two data collection instruments, (1) participants' background information and dress preferences form and (2) a focus group discussion questionnaire. The focus group discussion focused on marketing, clothing size, and questions about hijab, abaya fashion, and problems of abaya. Participants were asked about their interest in abaya fashion, and the topic was introduced to wearing abaya women in Pakistan. Transition questions followed, followed by core questions that explored each topic further. The study also included questions about religious and non-religious reactions and whether the abaya is a personal choice or a forced choice by families. Twelve inquiries were conducted to gather data on the design preferences of individuals regarding their abaya's problems. Participants were also required to provide their demographic and psychographic details such as age income educational qualifications about traditional and religious events or activities. Four women were chosen as the experimental group to pre-test data collection instruments, focus group discussion questionnaire, and participants' background information. The instruments were revised based on the focus group discussion.

I make a Survey form for Qualitative Research. Students from different cities fill out the form. I collect data from 85 girls at Gift University. Qualitative data were collected to determine the Islamic dress standards and Requests of Pakistani Muslim women. Gift University women were Interviewed. My friend is qualified to help in participant selection, applying a method of purposive sampling. This friend contacted hijab-wearing women from different cities in GIFT UNIVERSITY. The majority of participants were aware of the volunteer. There was a total of twenty-five ladies who confirmed that they wore an abaya or hijab. All participants studied at university. Most of the participants are teachers, housewives, students, and working women. The range of ages of participants were the oldest 42 years while the youngest was 18 years. Most of the participants are teachers, housewives, students, and working women. They need comfort clothing to solve abaya problems. The range of ages of participants were the oldest 42 years while the youngest was 18 years. I chose participants who wear an abaya Daily at the university.

Every single woman completed high school, with 65% holding bachelor's degrees and 31% holding master's degrees. 52% of the women's yearly income fell between \$7,000 and \$11,000, 24% fell between \$13,000 and \$14,000, and 5% fell between \$15,000 and \$17,000. 53% of the female participants stated shopping "frequently," 15% "infrequently," and 28% "sometimes." On Thursday, the focus group talks took place in the university hall. The personal information and clothing design preference form was filled out by each participant as part of a written exercise. Each of the two-hour sessions was observed by a member of our study team taking notes. All the interviewees took part in a written activity and completed the personal information form. One of our research team members took notes during the interviews, and each interview lasted 30–68 minutes. They want to adopt modern fashion trends within modesty. At private gatherings, women often remove their abayas, showcasing their Western-style attire.

My own experience at Gift University Gujranwala was very insightful. I visited Gujranwala in 2021 as a guest of the Gift College girls' campus during the gala festival. I was invited to numerous Pakistani students and friends during my tour, and I also went to a birthday party. My host advised me to wear a headscarf when I arrived at the party, and so did the other attendees. We were led into a quiet room where just ladies conversing, dancing, and eating. We removed our abayas as soon as we walked into the room and placed them in the corner pile. Looking around, I noticed that the females were dressed in showy Western attire beneath their tight jeans, halter tops that showed off their belts, high heels, and brand outfits. They certainly didn't let their gorgeous outfits show off to one another at the party, if not to any potential suitors, because the abaya covered them up. There was dancing, and the celebration was

unlike any other. At the end of the party, the women put their abayas on again before leaving and walked out of the living area. There would have been no way for someone from outside to know the comfortable, candid attitude that had taken over the room.

Results

We assessed the results of an online survey we did quantitatively on women and their abayas. to ascertain the issues and requirements of clothes for the elderly. The survey samples were divided up into four age groups. Under 18 years old (often referred to as "Girls" or "Adolescents"), 18-24 years old (Young Adults), 25-34 years old (Young Adults/Early Adulthood), 35-44 years old (Mid-Adulthood) see Figure 1.

Figure 1. Age Factor

We performed women's evaluations of the current abaya clothes in addition to doing in-depth research and analysis on the specifics of the modest fashion, taking into account the current clothing issues as represented by the abaya and women in the questionnaire survey. Furthermore, the questionnaire sample data revealed that over 80% of the ladies experienced problems with their abaya and thought there were faults with the current garment. Consequently, we carried out in-depth online survey interviews with 302 participants and an observational study on women's abayas.

Based on the data collected from the questionnaire, it was determined that the majority of women individuals prioritize wearing comfortable clothing over pricing when making wardrobe decisions. 83.2% are single women and 16.8% are married. Of the occupations of participants, 47 are housewives, 65 are teachers, 176 are students and 8 are others. According to data analyses, women's 31.5% several times a week wear an abaya, 18.5% once a week, 4% rarely, and 45.6% daily wear an abaya (see Figure 2). The aim of abaya wear is for 132 comfort, 80 style, 47 modesty, 38 Cultural/Religious norms, and others, etc.

In terms of abaya problems, 95.6% have yes answers and 4.4% have No problems with their abayas (see Figure 3). If yes apply, then what problems do you face while performing their work (see Figure 4)? 131 Discomfort during physical activities (e.g., bike rides, stairs, High heel), Sleeve length 10, Issues with sizing (e.g., too long, too loose) 32, Lack of representation in the fashion industry 15, Escalator trap 5 and 101 participants all problems. They also agree to make reversible abaya (see Figure 5). They are satisfied with the functionality of abayas that can be worn in multiple ways (e.g., suit, dress, short and long) (see Figure 6).

Figure 2. Wear an Abaya

Figure 3. Abaya Create Any Problems while Performing Work

Figure 4. Problem During Work

Figure 5. Reversible Abaya

Figure 6. Functionally of Abaya

The number of agreed women is 278 in need of reversible abaya, Reversible abayas provide users the freedom to express themselves in a variety of contexts by combining traditional and modern styles. These clothes provide ladies the ability to style one piece into many styles by using reversible components like dual colors, patterns, or textures. Reversible abayas easily accommodate the many demands of contemporary living, whether they are worn for formal occasions, informal outings, or everyday events.

Discussion

I collect all information in written form document. When I interview Gift University students, I learn a lot of information. every participant gives me a different point of view about abaya problems. I am also an Abaya lover as a Fashion designer I collect data and analyze it. Women want to hide their body curves. They are casual use to abaya and no brand in Pakistan available abaya problems solve. I identify the needs of women. what she wants in design is simplicity shown in the abaya. In university events, they take clothes from home for events but it is a hassle. They want to design a kind of abaya that is convertible in a short dress for attending events. Women also have problems with a hijab with masks. Elastic Face Mask use causes ear pain. Even with single masks, one of the most common complaints among healthcare workers who are wearing tight-fitting coverings for hours each day has been ear soreness. Abaya contrast

Hijab is not stylish in Pakistan. Tripping on stairs 70 %, Size matters a lot in Abaya 30%, During bike ride 75%, Design of abaya not good 45%, Fabric quality low 35%, Escalator trap 30%.

The advent of the Internet has transformed the world into a global village, allowing people to follow the latest fashion trends from all corners of the globe. In our research, abaya-wearing women expressed the view that abaya fashion deserves more attention in Pakistan. They felt that their needs were not adequately addressed and believed that hijabs and abayas should draw inspiration from the latest fashion trends. Additionally, participants emphasized the importance of introducing various designs and size ranges to cater to a broader market. However, it's essential to acknowledge the limitations of our study. The focus group was relatively small, and all participants were well-educated. As a result, the findings may differ when considering a larger and more diverse sample group, including less educated women.

The study highlights the need for retailers and manufacturers to attract more consumers in the abaya fashion market. While some progress has been made in blending Western fashion with cultural clothing, more efforts are needed, particularly in adding hijab and abaya designs to retailers' catalogs. Proper advertisements and marketing through fashion shows and seminars are also recommended. Manufacturers and retailers should pay closer attention to demographics, distinguishing between high, lower, and middle-class consumers, and offering quality and affordable options.

The suggestions provided were limited in their ability to effectively address the needs of women.

- a) The study underscores the need for improved abaya fashion representation and inclusivity in Pakistan.
- b) Advocates for a contemporary approach to hijab designs.
- c) Calls for a wider abaya size range.
- d) Stresses equal consideration of abayas in design and marketing.
- e) Calls for greater attention to hijab fashion in Pakistan.
- f) Introducing abaya designs that are comfortable and solve abaya problems.

In this sample for abaya size, I add a double side loop a type of rushing technique (Figure 7). We can change a short dress into a long Abaya.

(a) Sample

(b) Functional

Figure 7. Practical Design 1

Fusion of minimalism art with modest fashion. I use different shapes of art in my collection. Black and white color contrast. A mood board is a masterpiece of geometric art where modest fashion meets the modern world. My mood board modesty represents that mode, stylish and trendy wear. Mod means modest fashion + malist means simplicity. Islam gives the order of modesty. Harmony colors are black and white.

Conclusion

My research concludes that interviews were conducted to identify the problems of abaya during work like tripping on stairs, bike rides, length of abaya and high heel, etc. The text suggests that addressing the challenges faced by Abaya wearers necessitates a comprehensive approach that prioritizes comfort, functionality, and inclusivity. Innovative design solutions and responsive manufacturing practices can improve the Abaya wearer experience, allowing them to embrace their cultural heritage and religious identity. As the modest fashion industry evolves, efforts must be made to create garments that cater to modern consumer preferences, ensuring the Abaya tradition remains relevant and accessible for future generations. During data collection, we found out that Muslim women in Pakistan cover their heads to show respect, and believe in themselves, considered to requirement for a Muslim girl. I also found out that Muslim women are satisfied with their Modest fashion, therefore I focus on modest modern costumes. My research solves abaya problems. I also innovate the reversible abaya wear that transforms your mood. One of the concepts this study provided is “modest fashion, modern, minimalist”. In Pakistan, there are hundreds of fashion labels, but no one is particularly focused on these abaya problems.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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